

Synthesis of 2-Amino Thiazole Derivatives

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Synthesis of 2-amino thiazole derivatives and their effect on blood sugar are studied.

FROM the therapeutic point of view thiazole derivatives are of considerable interest, since their utility in the treatment of diseases has been firmly established^{1,2}. Thiazole derivatives contain thiourea moiety and, therefore, like urea derivatives can possibly act as hypo/hyper glycaemic agents^{3,4}. In view of these possibilities, variously substituted thiazole derivatives were synthesised (Table 1) and some of them were tested for their biological properties.

4(Substituted phenyl)-2-amino thiazoles were prepared by Dodson and Kings' method and also by Hantzsch thiazole synthesis. The acetophenones and 2-haloketones required for the above synthesis were prepared by Fries migration and Fridel-Craft reaction respectively. 5-Carboxy-4-(substituted)-2-amino-thiazoles were prepared by Dodson and Kings' method. The β -ketoesters required for the preparation of the above thiazole derivatives were prepared by the methods

TABLE 1—MELTING POINTS AND ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF 2-AMINO THIAZOLES

No.	2-Amino-thiazole (Only 4-phenyl substituent is given)	M.P °C	Yield %	Formula	Carbon %		Hydrogen %	
					Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
1.	4-(2'-Hydroxy-4'-chloro-phenyl)-	183-5 (220)	40	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ ClOS	47.68	47.75	3.09	2.96
2.	4-(2'-Hydroxy-4'-bromo-phenyl)-	197 (254)	35	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ BrOS	39.85	39.96	2.58	2.48
3.	4-(2'-Hydroxy-4'-iodo-phenyl)-	216 (285)	40	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ IOS	33.96	34.36	2.20	1.50
4.	4-(2'-Chloro-4'-hydroxy-phenyl)-	148 (130)	20	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ ClOS	47.85	46.99	3.09	2.14
5.	4-(3',4'-Dichlorophenyl)-	153 (250)	70	C ₉ H ₆ N ₂ Cl ₂ S	44.08	44.13	2.44	2.40
6.	4-(2',5'-Dichlorophenyl)-	169 (164)	70	C ₉ H ₆ N ₂ Cl ₂ S	44.08	44.14	2.44	3.10
7.	4-(2'-Chloro-5'-methyl-phenyl)-	120 (139)	70	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ ClS	53.46	53.49	4.02	4.36
8.	4-(2'-Bromo-5'-methyl-phenyl)-	95 (151)	60	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ BrS	44.67	44.70	3.34	3.55
9.	5-Carboxy-4-(2'-methyl-phenyl)-	175	30	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃ S	59.54	59.32	5.34	4.70
10.	5-Carboxy-4-(3'-methyl-phenyl)-	173	30	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃ S	59.54	59.04	5.34	5.52
11.	5-Carboxy-4-(4'-methyl-phenyl)-	134	40	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃ S	59.54	59.17	5.34	4.98
12.	5-Carboxy-4-(4'-nitro-phenyl)-	225	60	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄ S	49.15	49.99	3.75	2.82
13.	5-Carboxy-4-(2-furyl)-	137	30	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ S	50.42	50.14	4.20	2.55
14.	5-Carboxy-4-(2-thienyl)-	165	30	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	47.25	46.84	3.39	2.80

The bracket figures represent the melting points of their hydroiodides (No. 1 to 4) and hydrochlorides (5 to 8).

described by Straley and Adams⁵ while in literature these are synthesised by Claisen condensation.

The following acetophenones, 2-haloketones and β -keto esters were used in this work :

1. 2'-Hydroxy-4'-chloro acetophenone.
2. 2'-Hydroxy-4'-bromo acetophenone.
3. 2'-Hydroxy-4'-hydroxy acetophenone.
4. 2'-Chloro-4'-hydroxy acetophenone.
5. 2,3',4'-Trichloro acetophenone.
6. 2,2',5'-Trichloro acetophenone.
7. 2,2'-Dichloro-5'-methyl acetophenone.
8. 2-Chloro-2'-Bromo-5'-methyl acetophenone.
9. Ethyl-(*o*-toluoyl)-acetate.
10. Ethyl-(*m*-toluoyl)-acetate.

11. Ethyl-(*p*-toluoyl)-acetate.
12. Ethyl-(*p*-nitro benzoyl)-acetate.
13. Ethyl-(2-furoyl)-acetate.
14. Ethyl-(2-thenoyl)-acetate.

4-(Substituted phenyl)-2-aminothiazoles were converted into their sulphha derivatives by treating them with *p*-acetamido-benzene sulphonyl chloride and subsequent hydrolysis (Table 2).

2-Amino thiazoles (compound No. 5 and 6) are found to be identical to those reported in literature^{6,7}. The structures of these 2-amino thiazoles were confirmed on the basis of their melting points and elemental analysis.

TABLE 2—MELTING POINTS AND ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF 2-SULPHANILAMIDO THIAZOLES

No.	2-Sulphanilamido thiazole (only 4-phenyl substituent is given)	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	Carbon %		Hydrogen %	
				Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
1.	4-(2'-Hydroxy-4'-chloro-phenyl)-	175	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ ClO ₂ S ₂	47.19	45.90	3.19	4.52
2.	4-(2'-Hydroxy-4'-bromo-phenyl)-	184	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ BrO ₂ S ₂	44.68	44.09	3.12	2.56
3.	4-(3',4'-Dichloro phenyl)-	158	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ Cl ₂ O ₂ S ₂	45.00	44.77	2.75	3.80
4.	4-(2',5'-Dichlorophenyl)-	173	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ Cl ₂ O ₂ S ₂	45.00	45.32	2.75	2.86
5.	4-(2'-Chloro-5'-methyl-phenyl)-	95	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ ClO ₂ S ₂	50.59	50.82	3.68	2.48
6.	4-(2'-Bromo-5'-methyl-phenyl)-	85	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ BrO ₂ S ₂	45.28	44.89	3.30	2.80

Fig. 1A

Fig. 1B

Fig. 1C

Fig. 1D

Hypo/hyperglycemic activity :

2-Amino thiazoles prepared in this work were tested for their hypo/hyper glycaemic activity. The activity was tested in normal rats (average weight 200 gm). They were divided into groups of seven and fed orally with test compounds (150 mg/kg) as solution in 5% tragacanth. Seven rats were kept as control. After every hour blood samples were drawn from tail veins for the measurements of glucose content. Changes in the glucose content in the blood of the tested rats were compared with that of the control groups at intervals of 1,2,4 and 48 hours in each case. The data of the *in vivo* activity tests of the above compounds are given (Table 3).

excess of iodine and unreacted acetophenone. It was then extracted with boiling water and filtered hot to remove solid impurities. The filtrate on cooling gave a reddish brown solid, which upon crystallisation from aqueous ethanol gave needles.

The hydroiodide obtained above was dissolved in water and neutralised with concentrated ammonia solution when a yellow coloured free base was obtained. It was then crystallised from ethanol.

Hantzsch thiazole synthesis : (Fig. 1 B).

A mixture of 2-halo ketone (0.01 mole), thiourea (0.013 mole) and alcohol (10 ml) was refluxed for one

TABLE 3—HYPO/HYPERGLYCEMIC ACTIVITY OF 2-AMINO THIAZOLES

No. 2sAmino-thiazole (only 4-substituent is given)	Percentage increase (+) or decrease (-) of blood glucose effected by compound (b)			Results
	1 hr.	2 hrs.	4 hrs.	
1. 4-(2'-Hydroxy-4'-chlorophenyl)-	+13	+10	-3	hyperglycemic
2. 4-(2'-Hydroxy-4'-iodophenyl)-	+ 6	+ 5	-2	inactive
3. 4-(2'-Chloro-4'-hydroxyphenyl)-	- 5	- 4	-4	inactive
4. 4-(3',4'-Dichlorophenyl)-	- 4	- 5	-12	inactive
5. 4-(2',5'-Dichlorophenyl)-	+ 6	+ 6	+5	inactive
6. 5-Carbethoxy-4-(2'-methylphenyl)-	+ 3	+ 3	+16	hyperglycemic
7. 5-Carbethoxy-4-(4'-methylphenyl)-	+18	+31	+52	hyperglycemic
8. 5-Carbethoxy-4-(4'-nitrophenyl)-	-2	-4	zero	inactive
9. 5-Carbethoxy-4-(2'-thienyl)-	-4	-2	zero	Inactive

(b) : Results and expressed as the percentage difference in mg. percent between the mean change in control treated groups after a drug dose of 150 mg/kg.

A compound is considered hypoglycemicly active if it produces 30% decrease in blood glucose and hyperglycemicly active if it produces 10% increase in blood glucose.

$$\text{Percentage change} = \frac{\Delta T - \Delta C}{\text{Control glucose value at that hour}}$$

ΔT = change of blood glucose from zero time for treated groups.

ΔC = change of blood glucose from zero time for control groups.

Experimental**Experiment No. 1.**

Preparation of 4-(substituted phenyl)-2-aminothiazoles : Dodson and Kings' method : (Fig. 1 A).

A mixture of acetophenone (0.01 mole), thiourea (0.02 mole) and iodine (0.01 mole) was heated on a steam bath for ten hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and repeatedly washed with ether to remove

and half hours. It was then cooled. The solid crystalline hydrochloride thus separated was filtered and washed with ether to remove unreacted ketone. It was then dried and crystallised from aqueous ethanol.

The hydrochloride obtained above was boiled with water and ammonium hydroxide solution. The solid thus obtained was filtered and washed with water. Crystallisation from 95% ethanol gave fine crystal of 2-aminothiazole.

Experiment No. 2 : (Fig. 1C).

Preparation of 5-(carbethoxy)-4-(substituted)-2-aminothiazoles.

A mixture of β -keto ester (0.05 mole), thiourea (0.1 mole) and iodine (0.05 mole) was heated on a steam bath for sixty hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and extracted with ether to remove unreacted β -keto ester and iodine. The residue was extracted with boiling water. On cooling, the hydroiodide was separated. It was neutralised by ammonia solution to get free amine. The solid thus obtained was filtered

and washed with ice cold water. Crystallisation from aqueous ethanol gave silky needles.

Experiment No. 3 :

Preparation of sulphanylamido thiazole : (Fig. 1 D).

A solution of 2-amino thiazole (0.015 mole) in dry pyridine (15 ml) was treated in portions with freshly prepared *p*-acetamidobenzene sulphonyl chloride (3 g). The reaction mixture was heated on a water bath for half an hour and then kept at room temperature for 48 hours. It was poured over crushed ice containing little sulphuric acid. The precipitated solid was filtered and washed with water. It was crystallised from 50% ethanol.

The acetyl sulphanylamido thiazole (1 g) obtained above was boiled with dilute hydrochloric acid (25 ml) and ethanol (5 ml) for half an hour. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and diluted with water. The sulphanylamido thiazole thus obtained was crystallised from aqueous ethanol.

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References

1. E. H. NORTHEY, *Chem. Revs.*, 1940, 27, 85.
2. M. R. A. CHANCE, P. DIRNHUBER and F. A. ROBINSON, *Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1946, 1, 153.
3. J. C. KARNTZ and C. J. CARR, "Pharmacologic principles of medical practice, 6th ed. Williams and Wilkins Co. 1967, p. 865.
4. M. Y. MHASALKAR, M. H. SHAH, K. G. ANANTNARAYAN and C. V. DELIVALA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1971, 14(10), 260; 1970, 13(4), 672.
5. J. M. STRALEY and A. C. ADAMS, "Organic syntheses", Col. Vol. IV, Edited by Rabjohn, John Wiley and Sons, 1963, p. 415.
6. J. B. DICKEY, E. B. TOWNE, M. S. BLOOM, W. H. MOORE, H. M. HILL, H. HEYNEMANN, D. G. HEFBERG, D. C. SIEVERS and M. V. OTIS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, 24, 187.
7. *Chem. Abs.*, 1973, 78, 184394 c.